

The Students Journey in Crossing the Threshold of Reality: Lived Experiences of Nursing Students in Online Learning

¹Ryan L. Vallejo, ²Angelica Angeles, ³Kemberly Argallon, ⁴Ma. Victoria Collantes, ⁵Carmishayne Joy Bartolome

^{1,2,3,4,5} Mary Chiles College Manila, City of Manila, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7268186>

Published Date: 31-October-2022

Abstract: The researchers utilized Colaizzi's seven Phenomenological Approaches in the research model to answer the Grand Tour Question, "How do you describe the online learning education?" Thus, the participants who took part in online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic were subjected to emotional and psychological advantages and disadvantages associated with their thoughts, feelings, and behavioral responses to the online learning experience. The study also showed that while online learning is a viable substitute for traditional education, some participants perceived environmental factors that hindered the learning process; hence, the online learning hindered and challenged participants from coping with the current circumstances, given the ability to cope. Therefore, the researcher concluded that although a certain proportion of participants stated that online learning provides a positive outcome in terms of academic performance, most of the participants still emphasized their concerns regarding their experiences in online education. Every statement was identified as being in the same situation as one another. The researchers also concluded that themes and subthemes are also interrelated; this means that when a problem a participant perceives is present, it also affects their other concerns, which can be seen as a connection. The researchers finally concluded that emotional and psychological experiences, perceived complements, perceived challenges, environmental barriers to learning, and adaptation approaches to online learning all were answered the study's main question, "How do you describe your online learning experiences?"

Keywords: BSN students, online education, coping mechanisms, learning experiences.

I. INTRODUCTION

The current pandemic has caused a lot of differences and introduced a new trend for those people in the field of health care education, especially in the field of nursing education, where online learning education has been applied. However, some questions were asked, such as how do nursing students cope with such a new and different approach to learning and how do they describe this learning environment? These questions and trends led the curious minds of the researchers from Mary Chiles College of Nursing to conduct a Qualitative Type Phenomenological Study. The researchers' sole aim was to know and understand the experiences regarding online learning education among the Bachelor of Science in Nursing students from Mary Chiles College Manila. "Online learning is not the only avenue to constructivist learning, but it is uniquely designed to enable such self-learning" (Rovai). This statement implies that online learning does not only build knowledge and information but also generates experiences. Given this statement, a researcher with a curiosity wants to explore the experiences of level 2 and 3 nursing students during this time of the pandemic—the shift from the traditional education system, commonly known as face-to-face, to asynchronous and synchronous learning. Online learning education was used for those in the field of health care education, particularly in the field of nursing education. However,

the question that has developed: how do nursing students cope with such a new and different approach to learning and how do they describe this learning environment? Hence, these questions and trends led the innovative and curious minds of the researchers from Mary Chiles College of Nursing to conduct a Qualitative Type Phenomenological Study. The researchers solely aim to know and understand the experiences with regards to online learning education of Bachelor of Science in Nursing students from Mary Chiles College Manila.

The researchers utilized the model of Colaizzi's seven Phenomenological Approaches in Research to answer the Grand Tour Question, "How do you describe online learning education?" The first step is called "Familiarization," wherein the researchers will familiarize themselves with the accounts of the participant's experiences with regard to online learning education. The second step is to identify significant statements from the participants' accounts. This is why the first step is important so that similar accounts can be easily identified. The third step will be formulating meanings from the similar experiences identified. Bracketing will be utilized in this step. The fourth step is clustering themes. The researcher will identify and cluster themes based on the generated meaning from the previous step. The fifth step is developing a detailed description, wherein the researchers write a complete and inclusive description based on the generated cluster themes. The sixth step is producing the fundamental structure. With this step, the researcher condenses and summarizes important reports to develop a short statement that targets an essential structure of the phenomena. The last step in verifying the fundamental structure was for the researchers to go back to the fundamental structure and verify with the participants if their accounts matched the generated fundamental design. This study explores the experiences of learners in the field of nursing in relation to the COVID-19 Pandemic. A phenomenon in the field of education resulted in the transition of the mode of learning in the field of nursing from face-to-face to online. Hence, the s Online learning is education that is conducted over the internet. It may sometimes be referred to as "e-learning," specifically synchronous and asynchronous learning. This is done using e-mail, discussion boards, video conferencing, instant messaging, and chat, as well as face-to-face meetings. According to Heap (2017), students can look for a place or an environment that will work best for them, a place that will more likely motivate these students to study. Listening to lecture podcasts while running on the treadmill in the bedroom, study room, a cafe across the street, or in the local gym, students won't need to go to their classes to commute for hours. In contrast, according to one study of digital learning, only half the students will sign up for online group activities. As such, peer-to-peer engagement is lower in e-learning than in classroom-based learning.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

This study further explores the online learning experiences of nursing students and how online learning will benefit them in their academic performance. It will also provide an understanding of the perspective of students towards online learning, which may affect their academic performance either positively or negatively. For instance, the time that was supposed to be spent studying was used for commuting, which is vital for students who use time efficiently. The less time spent on commuting or driving a car, the better. This signifies the time spent studying and reading all the modules. Therefore, this study may help students fit their work schedules and coursework more easily. Thence, the use of qualitative research in this study seeks to collect and analyze non-numerical data to understand concepts, opinions, or experiences. It can also be used to gather in-depth insights into a problem or generate new ideas for research study identified the fundamental structure that describes the learning experiences of respondents during online learning.

III. RESEARCH DESIGN

The researchers used the Qualitative Descriptive Phenomenological approach as the research design of the study to come up with themes and generate a fundamental structure that will describe the current online learning experiences of nursing students from level 2 and 3. The Qualitative Descriptive Phenomenological Approach is a type of qualitative research that focuses on the careful portrayal of ordinary conscious experience of everyday life, a depiction of "things" as people experience them. These "things" include hearing, seeing, believing, feeling, remembering, deciding, and evaluating (Polit and Beck, 2018). Descriptive phenomenological studies often involve the following four steps: bracketing, intuiting, analyzing, and describing. However, this study will particularly utilize the model of Colaizzi's seven Phenomenological Approaches in Research. This research design is suitable to the research grand tour question which is "How do you describe the online Learning Education?" for the reason that by definition Qualitative Descriptive Phenomenological approach is use to describe how human beings experience a certain phenomenon which in this research focus on the online learning experiences of Nursing students from Mary Chiles College level 2 and 3.

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (166-189), Month: September - December 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

THE ROLE OF THE RESEARCHER:

The part of the researcher in this phenomenological study was based on the seven steps of the Colaizzi phenomenological study. In the process of the study, the researchers familiarized themselves with gathered data, identified meaning from it, formulated meanings, clustered themes, developed exhaustive descriptions, produced fundamental structures, and sought verification. Since the researchers used a descriptive phenomenological study, the researchers themselves developed an instrument for the survey, whereas they would be the people to interview the participants and explore their experiences.

SELECTING PARTICIPANTS

The participants of this study were from Mary Chiles College of Nursing levels 2 and 3. The participants were chosen based on a method called the purposive sampling approach. The main objective of a purposive sample was to produce a sample that could be logically assumed to be representative of the population. The researchers needed 2 participants from level 2 and 3 participants from level 3 nursing students. The participants were from Nursing Student level 2 and 3 only because these students had already experienced what nursing school is.

THE SETTING

Respondents are nursing students at levels 2 and 3 from Mary Chiles College since they have more experience and background in the environment that they are currently in. Purposive sampling will be used, which selects a particular subset of people who could give very detailed information. According to Black, K. (2010), the purposive sampling method may prove to be effective when only a limited number of people can serve as primary data sources due to the nature of the research design and aims and objectives. The chosen respondents are 2nd-year and 3rd-year college students. An interview will be held through Zoom, Google Meet, and other online platforms within an allotted time frame. The researchers gathered not only the responses but also observed the way participants spoke and acted on camera. The data will be documented through the use of a pen, paper, and recorder for data analysis. The goal was to explore the experiences in online learning and whether the respondents were also willing to give their knowledge based on experience, within their availability, and with their consent. This is to ensure the participants' comfort. This study allowed potential research participants to freely participate in the study. This study also ensures that any information collected will be confidential at all costs. This would be discussed with the respondents before letting them answer the questions. The model used by the researchers is the Colaizzi Seven Phenomenological Approach in Research Answering the Grand Tour Question. Qualitative research methodology since one of the goals of the study is to gain a deep understanding of a specific event or phenomenon, which is an online learning and any patterns that can be found among a group of participants.

GENERATING DATA

The criteria for inclusion required that the participants must be enrolled in Mary Chiles College of Nursing levels 2 and 3, and they were willing to share their experiences with online learning. The participants would also be given an explanation and instruction of the study and an opportunity to ask free questions, particularly about their involvement in the interview study. Participants were notified beforehand about the study through a letter. Once they agreed to participate, the researcher met them at their preferred time to further describe the purpose of the study in detail, and then written consent was obtained. The average length of the interview was 30 min., which depends on the willingness of the participants. The discussion started with a casual conversation, which allowed the participants to adjust to the interview. The researchers also made the interview appear and built a rapport as if they were listening to a friend's story. While talking, it is advisable to never interrupt the participants, even when some of the answers are not so important. The conversation was guided by the central question: how do you describe your online learning experience? and will be followed by the sub-questions stated above. The interview continued for those who were willing to go beyond the allotted time. The conversation was recorded, as were the field notes for the participant's physical appearance and gestures during the interview. After the interview, the participant's reaction was written on the researcher's field notes, including the researcher's initial personal impression and analysis.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS:

In this study, the participants will be asked for permission to be included in the study. A soft copy of printed consent will be given before the start of the interview. Furthermore, the right of the respondents to full information will be consider. Likewise, explanation of the purpose of the study will be emphasize. Confidentiality of information and identity will be

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (166-189), Month: September - December 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

recognized by not using their real names, thus the names that appear in the participant's profile will be pseudonyms. Queries will be answered by the researchers and an informed consent will be signed by the respondents to protect both parties. Materials like recorders, papers and pencil for taking down notes will be utilized during the data gathering and will also be explained to the participants and therefore will be placed where it is visible to them. The data will be kept confidential for the duration of the study. On completion of the research, they will be retained for a further six months and then destroyed.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

In the first step, the researchers read a description of each person participating in the study to gain a sense of the participants. Next, the researcher would extract statements with significance to the research question, such as descriptions of how a first-time father feels about caring for a newborn. To reflect the research data accurately, the significant statements should be direct quotations from the participants. To analyze the significant statements, the researchers begin to articulate what the statements mean and create themes from the meanings. The researcher grouped similar themes together and organized them into categories. Finally, the researcher integrates the results into a comprehensive description of the topic and returns to each participant to verify the results (Writer, 2020). "These steps were utilized for data analysis.

Grand Tour Question:

How do you describe your online learning Experience?

Sub questions:

1. How does online learning benefit you?
2. What are the challenges that you have encountered during online learning?
3. What are the advantages and disadvantages of online classes for you as a nursing student?
4. How do you cope with online learning?
5. How do you perceive the quality of online learning from your experience?
6. What new practices do you develop in online learning?

The information needed to answer the above questions was gathered from participants in March 2021. The information taken from the participants was video recorded, transcribed, directly quoted, and analyzed using Colaizzi's Phenomenological Approach. The findings were analyzed and discussed in the literature, along with the facts obtained from the interview. Using the theories and principles, the researchers came up with discussions and conclusions based on the actual interpretation and analysis. The analysis considered how each participant manifested and imparted their experience during the online class. In this way, the researchers could focus on the involvement of nursing students in implementing online classes during the pandemic.

Looking back in 2020, the participants had a pleasant college life experience at Mary Chiles College. They mentioned how they value interaction and physical presence in teaching where they can grasp the whole idea of what a nurse should be doing. As the news of class suspension due to the COVID-19 pandemic came into view, the participants felt new to the sudden change in an educational environment as they tried to adjust to the new normal of interaction using gadgets for educational purposes. Some had difficulty coping, while others had an average experience depending on the available resources and the environment, they are currently living in. It is also important to note that several nursing students also experienced significant challenges during this time of pandemic as they focused more on their online classes. They also experience anxiety, lack of support systems, lack of motivation, and tend to compare themselves to others on given occasions, which can be a potential hindrance for them in their studies.

ANALYSIS OF THEMES

The researchers created the themes based on the existing sub-themes that define a particular phenomenon. The sub-themes were formulated based on the first and second steps of the Colaizzi Phenomenological Approach; the first and second steps were familiarization and identifying significant statements. The first created theme is called "Emotional and Psychological Experiences." The first themes and subthemes show the emotional and psychological experiences of the

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (166-189), Month: September - December 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

participants during online learning. The second theme is called "Perceived Complements," resulting from online teaching and learning methodology. The second theme identifies the perceived positive effects of online learning on participants. The third theme, entitled "Perceived Challenges," resulted from the online teaching and learning methodology. The third theme is contrary to the second theme as it shows the negative experiences of participants during online learning. The fourth theme, entitled "Environmental Barriers to Learning," solely focuses on the environmental barriers that hinder the participants from learning during online classes. The fifth theme, entitled Adaptation Approaches to Online Learning, shows how the participants cope with and adapt to online learning. The themes and subthemes created show a direct visualization of the phenomena being studied. It offers particular experiences, perceived complement, challenges, barriers and how the participants cope with those challenges and barriers. This outlines the experiences of nursing students as they engage in online learning.

Summary of Themes**THEME 1 - Emotional and Psychological Experiences****SUBTHEMES:**

- A Lack of motivation
- B. Adjustment to online learning
- C. Lack of confidence
- D. Anxiety due to lack of support system
- E. Comparing self to others

THEME 2- Perceived Complements resulted from online teaching and learning methodology.**SUBTHEMES:**

- A. Online learning is convenient
- B. Online learning as best substitute to face to face classes
- C. Availability of learning sources
- D. Independent learning
- E. Recognizing efforts of professors

THEME 3- Perceived Challenges resulted from online teaching and learning methodology.**SUBTHEMES:**

- A. Physical presence of teaching
- B. Online learning is challenging
- C. Application to profession
- D. Communication problem
- E. Insufficient learning method
- F. No learning benefits
- G Relying too much on technology
- H. Limited virtual discussion

THEME 4 – Environmental Barriers to Learning**SUBTHEMES:**

- A. Internet connection issue

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (166-189), Month: September - December 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

B. Unconducive learning environment

C. Lack of technical skills

D. Limited learning resources

THEME 5 – Adaptation Approaches to Online Learning

SUBTHEMES:

A. Time management

B. Pacing options

C. Leisure to cope

D. Technical skills to use gadgets for online learning

E. Multitasking

F. Always updated

THEME 1 - Emotional and Psychological Experiences

Online learning creates new experiences for every learner upon undergoing the Colaizzi Phenomenological Steps. The participants showed common experiences as they engaged with online learning, which pertains to emotional and psychological experiences such as lack of motivation, adjustment to online learning, lack of confidence, anxiety due to lack of support system, and comparing oneself to others.

SUBTHEMES:

A. Lack of motivation

The shift from face-to-face to online learning poses modifications to the educational system. This rapid shift creates an experience that learners encounter as they engage in online learning, and a lack of motivation is one of those. Lack of motivation is the absence or deficiency in interest, desire, and driving force of learners as they engage in online learning. Participants showed a lack of motivation as no one encouraged them to continue learning their chosen courses. Participants do not have enough personal interactions and no willingness to continue pursuing their studies even under the new normal. The participants also lack the support system to enable them to continue learning online. This predisposed them to experience a lack of motivation. 'Naging challenge sa kinabang yung motivation kasi parang walang nagpupush sa kinabang na pumasok.'-(SN1) ("Motivation was a challenge for me because no one pushed me to attend classes.") -(SN1) 'Hindi ako motivated kasi walang personal interactions' (SN2) ("I'm not motivated because there were no personal interactions")-(SN2) According to Purdue University Global (2020), some online learners may start fully engaged and realize their motivation is diminishing. Online learning involves motivation to complete tasks, stay involved, and make progress. Similarly, when a physical setting does not surround classmates and instructors, putting off or delaying their jobs may be tempting. ("Another downside would be, I think, motivation. Since its online, it's so easy for us to just scroll through our lectures, sometimes even neglected.") (SN3) "Mahirap siya kasi nga yung anxiety parang less motivated ako through online, feeling ko baka di ko kayanin". (SN5) ('It's hard due to the anxiety since I am less motivated online. I feel like I can't manage.')-(SN5) "Sobrang hirap niya para sa kinabang hindi ako sanay so may mga times na demoted ako wala ako wisyo mag aral". (SN6) ('For me, it was too hard. I'm not used to it, so there are times when I'm demoted and have no will to study.')-(SN6) In the study of Baticulon et al. (2020), it was stated that teachers must understand learners' needs, motivations, and past experiences to maintain engagement in an online program. It simply means that motivation affects online learning, and a lack of motivation hinders learning. The study also considered that lack of motivation is a type of institutional barrier. This simply proves that lack of motivation is one of the experiences that learners encounter as they engage in online learning. Participants consider motivation a significant factor contributing to the learner's success as they engage in the learning process. Motivation from the participants' family, friends, classmates, and professors is lacking as participants engage in online learning. A lack of motivation makes it difficult for the participants to cope with online learning. Lack of motivation poses a great threat to the learner's success as it hinders the participant's the ability to accomplish their tasks and responsibilities as learners.

B. Adjustment to online learning

There is no doubt that online learning has now become a fundamental part of the educational system. However, a question has been raised in reinforcing the new learning set-up, and the questions being mostly asked are: "how effective is online learning?" And were the students able to adjust to the new learning system? The shift from face-to-face classes to online learning forced the participants to make adjustments and modifications in the learning process. Adjustment is the process of balancing conflicting needs or needs challenged by problems in the environment. Since traditional classes were changed to online classes, adjustments were made by the learners. Inability to adjust to the current situation of online learning predisposes learners to non-compliance with their requirements and tasks. The participants' failure to adjust as they engage in online learning hinders them from achieving their desired learning. One of the participants stated that they are still not used to the new learning setup and still need to adjust. Participants need to change because they have not yet built the right variations for the profound online learning that can be contributed to the behavior of the participant. This will increase anxiety because of not achieving peace with oneself and the environment. Thus, participants still had to undergo many adjustments/changes to achieve and maintain equilibrium. The study is to explore the online learning experiences, how participants should make adjustments, and to identify whether participants can adhere to in the study of Baticulon et al. (2020), due to an abrupt shift in curriculum delivery, a lot of students had to go through a simultaneous adjustment in learning styles. The study says that people who spent fewer hours studying online were less likely to agree that they could cope. Students need more time to adapt to and comprehend learning materials. "Siguro adjustment ayun kailangan natin na parang magcope din na kailangan natin magkaroon ng big adjustment dun sa bagong way ng pagtuturo." (SN1) ('Perhaps adjustment [on the new learning]; that in order to cope, we must make a big adjustment on the new learning method.')

(SN1) "Adaptation lang din kasi ito na yung new normal kesa naman sumugod tayo sa face to face"- (SN4) ('For me, it's the adaptation because it's the new normal rather than pursuing it face-to-face.')

(SN4) "Adapt lang ng adapt need nalang I set ang mind ko na magagawa ko siya kahit online learning at self-learning." -(SN5) ('It's adaptation and a mindset that I can make it even though it's online learning and self-learning.')

(SN5) "Hindi parin ako sanay, kailangan ko parin ng adjustment kaya siguro hindi parin ako nakaka-adjust kasi hindi ako sanay sa ganitong situation." (SN6) ('I am still not used to it. Maybe the reason I can't adjust is because I am not used to this kind of situation.')

(SN6). From the participants' perspective, online classes became unfathomable because of the sudden alteration of the curriculum without proper preparation from the students, which resulted in an inability to cope with the situations that are still new to the participants, such as return demonstrations without the actual handling of tools and analyzing cases that are hypothetical despite the experiences of online learning that they already had in the previous semester. This simply proves that adjustment to online learning is one of the experiences participants encounter as they engage in online learning. The adjustment to online learning contributes to the participant's success or failure in the learning process. An adjustment must be made in order to cope with the situation.

C. Lack of Confidence Self-confidence is described as a student's belief or trust in their ability to complete a task successfully (Kanza, 2016). According to Perkins (2018), self-confidence is linked to success, educational gains, conciliation, and a person's well-being, among other aspects, and the three variables that can impair self-confidence are self-efficacy, self-esteem, and self-compassion. The association between a student's confidence and academic performance is inextricably linked. The degree of confidence in learners is a critical factor in their academic achievement. Consequently, it can influence their personal goals as well as their educational goals. As online learning carries on, lack of confidence becomes one of the utmost concerns of students since they are having a hard time with online learning. Due to a lack of confidence, participants are hesitant to open their cameras during online discussions, reluctant to answer questions, and hesitant to get help from their professors. Morin (2020) stated that learners aren't engaged in online classes because of how they think and learn differently. Some learners were having trouble managing sensory input and increasing anxiety about being "on display" to the point that it challenged their engagement online. Moneva and Tribunalo (2020) indicated in their study that students with high levels of self-confidence could easily accomplish their tasks in school. Most of them are not afraid to participate in every activity. While those students who have low self-confidence showed low performance on tasks, they were hesitant to participate in every activity. ("It's so hard to show your skills in a recitation because not all of us are out there; not all of us can unmute ourselves and answer.") -(SN3) From a learner's perspective, asking questions has become harrowing, especially during synchronous classes where the time online is very limited. Students always worry about whether or not they bother their professors when they ask them questions behind the

camera or after synchronous classes. Lammers (2017) also mentioned in his article that asking questions and getting help is a bit embarrassing, especially when the learner is totally confused and thinks they will look foolish in front of the professor. If the learner were ever supplied with answers and help from a professor, it would increase the likelihood that they would invest more time and effort in the course, hence building their confidence. “Hirap din ng online learning na di ka basta makapag tanong sa mga professors” -(SN1) (“Online learning is too hard you can’t just ask questions to your professors.”) -(SN1) “Nahihirapan din kami na magtanong sa online.” -(SN2) (“It’s hard to ask questions online.”) -(SN2) From what it said, confidence is important in how a learner functions in an online classroom. If the learner shows shyness and unresponsiveness during synchronous and asynchronous classes, it also displays a lack of confidence in their ability to learn. Hence, the online class will be perceived as less beneficial, and participants will be discontented with their online learning. The participation of every learner in an online class is important for the learners’ learning to be assessed and evaluated by their professors and to know whether the online learning with that learner is effective or not. If the participants are not exhibiting confidence, this will affect their overall performance in class and can result in the ineffectiveness of online learning.

D. Anxiety due to lack of support system

The pandemic causes many educational changes, predisposing students to different experiences, including emotional and psychological experiences such as anxiety. Anxiety is a vague feeling of dread or apprehension. The support system is the participants’ network of facilities and people who interact and remain in informal communication for mutual assistance. A support system is considered an important factor in how learners maintain their functions and accomplish their tasks. Participants experience anxiety due to a lack of a support system as they engage in online learning. “Anxious kasi feeling ko baka di ko kayanin kasi wala yung mga friend ko na kasama ko mag aral, baka di ko kayanin kasi walang personal interaction with them.” -(SN5) (“I’m anxious because I feel that I won’t make it because my friends aren’t there to accompany me to study. I guess I wouldn’t make it because there was no personal interaction with them.”) -(SN5) Cleofas & Rocha (2021) stated that younger students and those enrolled in lower year levels exhibit higher levels of consequence-related COVID-19 anxiety compared to older counterparts. This signifies that online learning may cause anxiety. The lack of a support system and the cause of the pandemic make it difficult for students to cope with online learning. “Mahirap siya kasi nga yung anxiety parang less motivated ako through online, feeling ko baka di ko kayanin.” -(SN6) (“It was hard when anxiety strikes. I feel less motivated with this online [setup]. I feel like I won’t make it.”) -(SN6) Baticulon et al. (2020) stated that the epidemic had also led students to experience psychological stress, making it difficult for them to concentrate on their studies. They voiced worry, exhaustion, loneliness, homesickness, sadness, and hopelessness. The learners were concerned about online examinations, plans in medical school, potential training delays, and the safety of their families from COVID-19. To summarize, 86 percent of students reported having a mental health problem. This shows that anxiety caused by a lack of support systems is one of the emotional and psychological experiences that online learners feel and encounter.

E. Comparing Self to Others

Online learning has both negative and positive effects. The shift from traditional classes to online classes introduces new experiences to online learners. As participants engage in online learning, they tend to compare themselves to other learners. Take, for instance, the availability of learning resources. Not all online learners have a reliable internet connection and gadgets to use in learning. Not all learners have a conducive environment for learning, whereas face-to-face learners are comfortable learning in school. These are just some of the scenarios where learners tend to compare themselves to others.

According to Brouwer (2018), not all learners can access technological improvements. Today’s education is hampered by a digital gap that prevents all students from having equal access to the internet. Students who do not have access to the internet are missing out on a significant educational opportunity, which influences the country’s future. (“Someone who has a really fast internet connection may say that they have a better-quality experience for online learning, but someone who only uses data or phone data might say that they have a poor experience with online learning.”) -(SN3) “Hindi ako na stop sa pag-aaral kasi may mga studyante na nag stop dahil ayaw nila ng online learning.” -(SN4) (“I was able to continue my studies. However, some students weren’t able to continue because they were against online learning.”) -(SN4) “Hindi naman lahat ng students ay same level para yung iba ay hindi din mabilis maka catch up kaya sobrang

challenging sya.” -(SN5) (“Not all students are on the same level [of learning]. Others find it hard to catch up. That is why it is quite challenging.”) -(SN5) Therefore, comparing oneself to others contributes to the emotional and psychological experiences of a learner. Not every student gets an equal opportunity for education, and as a result, it interrupts and hinders learners' ability to learn as they engage in online learning.

THEME 2- Perceived Compliments resulted from online teaching and learning methodology.

Online learning has both positive and negative effects on learners. Theme 2 pertains to the participants' perceived compliments or feedback from their experiences as they engage in online learning. These perceived compliments are participants' positive views of the phenomenon in online learning. Perceived compliments resulting from online teaching and learning methodology include the availability of learning resources, independent learning, and recognition of professors' efforts; online learning is the best substitute for face-to-face classes.

SUBTHEMES:

A. Online learning is convenient

In the past, learners were accustomed to traditional learning methods like face-to-face learning. The usual scenarios would be waking up early in the morning, catching up on the daily transportation, and running to the first class that is scheduled for the day, sometimes hoping that being late is not a crime that has been accidentally committed. Conducting groupings and activities at that time is trouble-free since learners can easily group and communicate since they are already in the same room. But as we went along with the usual tradition, the COVID-19 pandemic suddenly happened. That made the learners and professors stay in the safety of their own homes. Hence, online learning was implemented by the government. At the same time, online classes became the new curriculum, forcing the learners to adapt to their new routine of attending classes, which means waking up not as early as usual, and with a short walk from bed to a nearby desk, the learner is now present in their class. Communication is still present, but not in the traditional sense. This time they can't see each other face-to-face but can create a little online room for them to be able to communicate. Online learning has a lot to offer despite its challenges, and it also showcases compliments that the participants consider a positive side as they engage in online learning. One perceived benefit of the online learning methodology is that it is considered convenient by participants. “Yung sa cost of living so sa kagaya naming na nasa province tapos nagmamamila parang mejo bumaba yung cost of living” (SN1) (“The cost of living, especially on my part, where I am in the province and go to Manila to study, slightly decreases the cost of my living.”) -(SN1) (“You know it's convenient to do it at the four corners of your room”) -(SN3). According to Regalado (2020), first and foremost, learners can participate in the discussion and lectures without riding the bus or jeepney for an hour or two. Another is that they can sit in on a class while nursing a common cold or wearing their most comfortable clothes and eating while doing the online activities. Those were just a few things that can be said about online learning. “Sakin mas okay na yung mag online classes para may matutunan ka ngayong lockdown dahil sa pandemic.”. (SN4) (“As for me, online classes are better [beneficial] so that you can learn something in this period of the pandemic.”). - (SN4). Some were perplexed by the initial shift to online learning, but there were benefits for students and professors with online learning, or a virtual classroom, as stated by Regalado (2020). Still, according to Regalado (2020), the application of technology is the key to restoring the flow of the disrupted classes. There is a rapid turn to platforms like Zoom, Facebook Messenger, Microsoft Teams, and the like. As stated, it is convenient for the participants to engage in online learning with the application of technology. “Ngayong online class video na lang pinapasa namin so para sa amin advantage yun kasi nagagawa namin at naeedit namin so mas nakakakuha kami ng mataas na grade” - (SN2) (“Now that it is an online class, we create, edit videos, and just submit them. It's an advantage for us because we can get a higher grade than usual.”) -(SN2) “Sa acads siguro mas accessible kasi one clicks mo lang anjan na yung mga kailangan mong resources and everything.” -(SN6) (“In terms of academics, it was more accessible. In just a click, everything you need is there, including resources.”) -(SN6) Online classes give considerable convenience to learners when it comes to complying with academic and personal life. It helps people be on time, communicate in any place they are currently at, and is cost-effective since they won't be traveling far and spend their money unless needed for the internet. According to the participants' statements, they are thankful for the accessibility of online learning and the thought that it was implemented to avoid wasting time that a learner should be used to attending class. With this convenience, the participants had a way to cope with the sudden transition from traditional to the online class, meaning to say that some learners viewed this online class as somehow beneficial.

B. Online learning as best substitute to face to face

Online learning is distance learning is a widely used distance education in today's pandemic situation because, besides the fact that online learning is the only distance education available as a substitute, there are so many different platforms under online learning that can make learning easier to grasp. According to Segaren (2020), there are five major benefits of online learning as an alternative to face-to-face interaction. By including web-based participation and interactive activities in your classes, online learning offers more opportunities to foster critical thinking skills. Although online classes have become profound, participants are enthusiastic about the new learning system because they see it as something to look forward to, as evidenced by their eagerness to learn new skills. Therefore, participants who experience excitement are open to changes and adjustments to online learning. "Exciting siya kasi yun nga diba ang dami ring natututunan na bagong skills" -(SN1)

("It's Exciting because we learn many new skills") -(SN1) "Kapag nagpapasa ng mga requirements mas nagiging detalyado yung napag- aralan mo mismo yung gagawin, mas prepared yung mga napapasa mo kagaya ng mga retdem" - (SN2) ("During submission of requirements, the process is more detailed and we can really study the task. We submit much better work like retdems.") -(SN2) "Dati sa face-to-face nasa school ka lang nag-aaral, pero ngayong online classes talagang madaming binibigay na activities kahit anong oras nagbibigay sila ng activities" -(SN4) ("Before, in face-to-face learning, you studied at school. But now, in online classes, they really are giving tons of activities. (SN4). Distance learning in clinical medical education amid the COVID-19 pandemic in Jordan: current situation, challenges, and perspectives Al-Balas, Al-Balas, Hasan, M., Aborajooh, E. et al. (2020) stated that "distance e-learning in medical education may be an alternative to traditional learning to deliver high-quality education." The availability of essential infrastructure and efficient institutional strategies represents a major challenge for integrating distance learning in medical education. Even though blended education (i.e., distance and on-campus) is well adopted in different world countries, the effect of distance electronic learning is likely to be revolutionary, especially in low-middle income countries." "Mas okay sakín yung ganitong setting kasi nga pandemic kaya feeling ko mas safe ako hindi ako high risk magkaroon ng covid" - (SN6) ("In this pandemic period, I prefer this type of setup. I feel safer and I am not at risk of acquiring COVID. ") - (SN6)

Thus, online learning provides opportunities to foster critical thinking resulting from the online teaching and learning methodology. Online learning is considered by the participants as the best option considering the risk of pandemic to achieve some learning.

C. Availability of learning resources

Learning resources are one of the pillars of learning because they make learning easier to grasp and attainable. Learning resources offer students a variety of approaches to completing a specific task. Learning resources facilitate the process of learning for both the learners and the professors. The availability of learning resources makes learning attainable. Online learning makes learning resources available and readily accessible using the internet. One of the perceived benefits of online learning is the availability of learning resources. ("You have your instruction materials, so you can just open your computer or your phone, and it's easy. You can be outside and still be taking quizzes and still be doing school work.") (SN3) ("I've got Google, so if there is anything that I need to make sure of, I've got my laptop, I've got my books with me, and I think using the technology or the materials that I have, I'm making sure that I'm learning the same amount of knowledge that I would if we were in classes.") -(SN3) "Need nalang ng internet at laptop lang" -(SN4) ("I just need an internet connection and a laptop") -(SN4). Tria, Z. (2020) cited in his study that "we are all staying in our homes due to the lockdown policy implemented by the government." However, learning should not halt. Different countries worldwide have introduced various solutions during the pandemic to continue the education process-the introduction of distance learning. "These are online learning platforms such as Google, TV broadcasts, guidelines, resources, video lectures, and online channels that were introduced" (UNESCO, 2020). The availability of learning resources during this pandemic makes students easier to cope with as they engage in online learning. This is one of the perceived benefits of online learning. Resources such as laptops, phones, and other gadgets connected to the internet. With these learning resources, learners would quickly obtain answers from the internet and be able to pass their requirements on time.

D. Independent learning

Independent learning is a learning process or a method where learners gain a wide range of knowledge by their actions. This type of learning may also provide students with the opportunity to self-discover themselves and their individual needs, as well as their perspective strengths and weaknesses. With these, the student would be expected to devote more time to self-independent study to get the most out of their experience. Due to the pandemic, the impact on remote education has underlined the need for students' self-directed learning. While students are accustomed to being monitored, guided, and strictly scheduled in their coursework and use of resources, including technological tools, school closures have forced them to become more independent in their learning. Independent way of learning the learners may set a certain level of freedom through which one can decide or set the pace according to which learners might want to study. According to Martineau (2020), work plans for making students more independent and responsible could be a helpful resource, provided that they are adapted for each student and each subject and that students are explicitly taught how to use them. Furthermore, work plans as an instructional tool might help students learn in normal circumstances by encouraging students to establish their objectives and practice self-discipline, as well as allowing them some influence over the techniques and instruments they use to complete tasks. "Nagbabasa basa na lang din ako" -(SN1) ("I'll just read for additional learning.") (SN1) "Ngayong po para magcope is nagbabasa na ng libro para may matutunan" -(SN2) ("As for now, in order to cope up I read books to learn something.") -(SN2) "I set ang mind ko na magagawa ko siya kahit online learning at self-learning" -(SN5) ("To have a mindset that I will be able to do it even in this online learning setup independently"). - (SN5) According to Chua E. and Seballuca B., students use all these e-learning platforms to be consistent with the academic requirements and balance the need for e-learning and studying their books. This just proves that students had established their goals as a result of online teaching and learning methodology, making each student underlined with self-directed learning/independent learning. Independent learning is a perceived complement that learners encounter as they engage in online learning.

E. Recognizing efforts of professors

Online learning is undoubtedly very exhausting, from making modules and videos to submitting documents. But with a good internet connection and the availability of resources, papers are somehow polished for both participants and professors. Recognizing the efforts of professors is something else. Identifying the steps is a chance to channel admiration that can help restore and enhance teachers' working circumstances despite pandemic situations. Some participants were able to cope with the online learning by recognizing the efforts of the professor. Participants appreciated professors who sent modules and PowerPoint presentations. This can reduce anxiety due to the availability of resources handed down by the professors. According to Winthrop (2020), "In the field of education, March 2020 will be remembered as the month when nearly all of the world's schools close their doors." Teachers reacted almost immediately to being asked to teach in new ways. They have videos of themselves doing experiments, developed materials for students with limited access to the Internet, and even demonstrated concepts outside their students' screen doors. Undoubtedly, instructors in all curriculum areas and throughout all sectors of education (public and private) are capable of extraordinary feats. They have excelled in this situation. According to Garcia (2020), amidst the pain many are enduring, there is a bright spot: Some teachers feel the appreciation is more profound than ever. Teachers and students are doing their best to continue their separate activities with the help of parents and communities. We're all reminded of what learning and teaching involve as we watch them: the mysteries inherent in each topic, the lectures, the assignments, the projects, and the questions, to name a few. But, as we've witnessed multiple times when instructors go above and beyond the call of duty, we've recognized that teaching is more than just these day-to-day duties. Teachers and students are doing their best to continue their separate activities with the help of parents and communities. We're all reminded of what learning and teaching involve as we watch them: the mysteries inherent in each topic, the lectures; the assignments; the projects; and the questions, to name a few. But, as we have witnessed multiple times when instructors go above and beyond the call of duty, we've recognized that teaching is more than just these day-to-day duties. "Siguro po yung with the help of teachers yung pagbibigay nila ng modules or mga online learnings dun po nakakapag cope kami" -(SN2) ("I guess the modules and other online learning activities given by our teacher from it we can cope up") -(SN2)B("This is a good way of studying at your own pace, learning all the modules and PowerPoint that the professors gave you"). -(SN3). In this period of the pandemic, OnePoll and Osmo data reveal that people are becoming more appreciative of the teacher's efforts. According to the study, "80 percent have a newfound respect for teachers; 77 percent feel teachers should be paid more; 69 percent feel teaching is tougher than their

present work; and 53 percent will take a greater interest in their child's education when the stay-at-home mandate ends.”
 “Kahit papano natuturuan naman tayo ng prof natin, ginagawa naman nila best nila para maturo satin yung kailangan sa mga practical na gagawin mga practices na gagawin yung mga demo” -(SN4) (“Our professors somehow teach us. They are giving their best for us to learn everything we need for the practicum or return demonstration.”) -(SN4). Thus, Perceived Complements resulting from online teaching and learning methodology in accordance to recognizing the efforts of professors during this pandemic are evident through interviews conducted believing people have a newfound respect for teachers and view teachers going beyond the call of duty.

THEME 3- Perceived Challenges resulted from online teaching and learning methodology

Online learning has both positive and negative effects on learners. The third theme is about the participants' perceived difficulties or barriers as they engage in online learning. The participants consider these perceived challenges as difficulties in learning. The perceived challenges are participants' negative views of their experiences in online learning. The physical presence of teaching online learning is challenging. Perceived challenges from online teaching and learning methodologies include application to the profession, communication problems, insufficient learning methods, no learning benefits, reliance on technology, and limited virtual discussion.

SUBTHEMES:

A. Physical presence of teaching

Physical presence in teaching means that learners prefer it when they see their professors face-to-face, as it helps them concentrate on the lesson and avoid getting distracted by other things. Professors have an impact as they make a real connection with learners, which fosters trust and appreciation in the classroom. The longing of learners for the physical presence of teaching is showing as they yearn for interaction, a live feed of demonstrations, and for instructors to be able to make direct contact with the learners, pay attention to what they say, and respond accordingly to whatever questions they may ask during class. In connection with the participants, they emphasize how they value the interconnectedness of an educator and a learner in the same room since it produces interaction, proper communication where a person transfers information to have a greater understanding, and hands-on performance to assess whether the learner's execution of a given tool is being carried out correctly. Al-Amin Md., Al Zubayer A., Deb B., et al. (2021) cited in their study that time-consuming feedback from teachers, unavailable professional and pedagogical assistance from educators, a lack of self-motivation, a lack of engagement, unappealing instructional methods, and course material are some of the opposing views of online learning. The lack of human contact, which was thought essential to create a peer support and in-depth community conversation on the topic, was a significant barrier to online learning. Also, Belgica C., Calugan A., Dumo J., et al. (2020) cited in their study that an online class eliminates the human connection and, therefore, student motivation, interaction, and the educator's ability to adapt course materials and presentations are somehow lost. With the lack of interaction during online classes, students tend to get distracted easily by smartphones, pets, deliveries, and many other things other than the ongoing online course. Because face-to-face interaction is absent, it is theorized that students will experience a lack of interest in online classes. “Sa disadvantage naman, siguro yung pagkakaroon ng kakulangan sa pagkakaroon ng interaction with the professors tapos sa interaction with our classmates hindi rin ganun yung pakikipag interaction (interact) sa mga classmate's mo na wala kayong bonding talaga”-(SN1) (“For disadvantage, there is a lack of interaction between the students and the professors. The same with our classmates, there is no bonding between us.”) -(SN1) “Yung learning ay hindi ma apply lalo na yung skills at hindi ako motivated kasi walang personal interactions” -(SN5) (“The learning can't be applied into practice, especially the skills, and I am not motivated because there are no interactions.”) -(SN5) Jones, I. (2011) stated that the actual appearance of a teacher in a brick-and-mortar or physical classroom is a primary indication that one has reached an institution of higher learning in the traditional college classroom. The picture conveys the sense that a teacher must be physically present in order to provide meaningful course material and manage student learning. One implication is that students must be in the same classroom as the teacher at the same time in order to listen, talk, and take part in the learning process. In the same study by Belgica, Calugan, Dumo, et al. (2020), they stated that the majority of learners still prefer face-to-face learning to online learning. One student remarked, “I learn more successfully if I meet my educator in person when discussing.” In a face-to-face class, the presence of the educator boosts the learner's confidence in their ability to learn more than in an online session. Another learner added: “Students listen to the teacher to be able to answer the activity, but they are not learning.” “Mas natututo

kapag inaactual talaga na sa face-to-face na harapan yung teacher and student.”-(SN2) (“Learning really occurs when it is actual when there is a face-to-face interaction between the teacher and the students.”) -(SN2) (Of course, nursing is such a holistic and practical profession, it’s not something we can learn online. “) -(SN3) “Iba parin talaga pag face to face nakikita mo siya personally hindi lang through the monitor” -(SN6) (Face-to-face learning is still different. You get to see him/her in person.) -(SN6). This proves that face-to-face interaction during class is highly favorable for both learners and educators to exchange information easily and create a holistic learning environment where learners can effectively learn their course and achieve professional interaction with a professor to establish good communication and performance. However, suppose participants do not achieve the expected physical presence of teaching. In that case, it will affect their ability to focus and distract them during online classes because of things surrounding them, such as the environment and the desire to check out social media online. This can cause them to do badly in class.

B. Online learning is challenging

Nothing is more inconvenient than dealing with internet issues while attempting to complete a task. Learning to wait an hour for a video to download, looking at a blank screen while it loads slowly, or having a crucial conversation with a professor drop isn't just inconvenient; it can also be detrimental to communication and demonstration. One of the challenges the learners studied was that the specifics of assignments, submitting those assignments, and various other duties would take more time than usual. As a result, pupils may be unable to keep up with the increased workload. (“I would describe it in one word: challenging. I find it very challenging, especially since I am not technologically inclined and I am not very used to surfing the internet or using Word, Excel, or PowerPoint, and you know, it’s challenging in a way that my computer skills also my organization and my attentiveness.”) -(SN3) According to Azzahra (2020), this proved to be challenging given issues like uneven access to the internet, the disparity in teacher qualifications and education quality, and the lack of information and communications technology skills. “Nakakachallenge din yung mga “demonstration kasi walang face to face interaction.”-(SN5) (“Demonstrations are challenging during online classes because there are no face-to-face interactions”) -(SN5) According to Baticulon R. (2020), students were concerned that they were not learning essential skills or getting ample patient exposure, a sentiment that is echoed around the globe. They also voiced the need to interact with peers with whom they could exchange insights, resources, and opinions. (“My online journey was not smooth; it’s tough for me, and I think I have a lot of things to do to make myself more motivated for this kind of learning.”) -(SN6) Respondents said that they needed more time to comprehend learning materials. Many admitted that they lacked self-discipline and drive to study. Educators must understand learners’ needs, motivations, and past experiences to maintain engagement in an online curriculum, according to Baticulon (2020). This proves that students engaged in this new online learning setup find it difficult to adjust, and with the quality of education, it is challenging for students to adapt to this new setup. Some of these challenges include being easily distracted and lacking personal interactions with their professors and others.

C. Application to profession

Application to a profession means that a person or a learner has managed to use their knowledge to apply it in a realistic scenario similar to their chosen career or course. In comparison, our participants are nursing students who should be hands-on with their work at all times, but because of a pandemic, medical schools around the world, including the Philippines, stopped face-to-face learning and abruptly shifted to the new normal, which became a problem for the participants of this study since every school shifted to online classes and stayed in the safety of their homes, which enables them to practice realistically as a preparation for their future profession. As they attempted to adjust to online learning, medical students in the Philippines encountered several interconnected challenges. These included applying their work to an actual scenario and interaction with a substantial patient. As an example, the learners are having a problem performing a proper NGT feed to a patient since they rely more on an improvised dummy. The learners won't respond when inserting a tube inside their nose, whether it hurts the patient or not. The same goes with formulating and establishing a good rapport with the patients. Since the learners will also interview a person that is easily accessible to them, they won't be able to interact appropriately with someone with the same case in the tools indicated only to assess someone with a certain kind of problem. According to Baticulon R.E., Sy J.J., Alberto N.R.I., et al. (2021), learners were worried that they were not developing critical skills or having enough patient exposure. The effect of online learning on optimizing management behavior and patient outcomes is still being debated due to a scarcity of well-designed research. No amount of online practice will replace the hands-on experience of delivering a newborn, aiding with trauma

laparotomy, or caring for a diabetic ketoacidosis patient from admission to discharge. As a result, all medical schools should have a plan for students to return to clinics. "Sobrang laking tulong ng magkakaroon kayo ng face to face syempre lalo na sa course natin na nursing kailangan natin syempre ng practice-based learning" -(SN1) ("It is a big help to have face-to-face classes for the reason that our course is nursing; we need practice-based learning.") -(SN1) "Nasa medical field kami kailangan talaga actual yung pagtuturo sa amin kaya para akin po mas maganda pa din face to face" -(SN2) ("We are on the medical field and it is really a need to have an actual teaching for this reason I still prefer face to face.") -(SN2) "Mahirap kasi kailangan natin talaga is yung face to face kailangan natin ng patient para ma practice natin yung learning natin sa course natin". -(SN4) ("It is hard because what we really need is face-to-face learning. We need a patient [an actual return demonstration] for us to be able to apply our knowledge in practice.") - (SN4) Although schools supplied alternatives for clinical duties or practices like lectures, case presentations, and simulation activities, the participants preferred actual situations where learners could grasp the problem and on-handedly learn all the lessons. Participants also believed that face-to-face interaction is crucial because it will provide them with access to more suitable people who have similar cases to what they are currently learning, so if a learner did not effectively practice their chosen courses in a more realistic way, it would negatively affect their performance when they dive into their medical areas in the future.

D. Communication Problem

Communication is a critical component of learning. It is very important to give instructions, responses, and clarifications, especially during online classes. Good communication makes the discussion stimulating and engaging for the learners. Communication affects learners' understanding of the discussed topic, whether verbal or nonverbal. However, online learning poses a threat to communication. The Philippines is considered one of the countries in Asia with a poor internet connection, and since the shift from face-to-face classes to online classes, there has still been little to no improvement. The Internet connection affects communication between the learners and their professors; it also includes audio clarity as instructions are given. This is considered one of the perceived challenges of online learning. ("Suddenly, you miss an important announcement or very important lesson that your professor is trying to tell you, or sometimes you get randomly kicked out because of poor internet connections") -(SN3) "Yung sa environment, communication, community, internet minsan di mo pa ma- gets yung lessons, pag follow up ganun kasi nga very limited lang yung time natin ngayong virtual" -(SN6) ("In terms of environment, communication, community, and internet, you don't understand the lessons, and due to very limited time in this virtual learning setup, it was hard to ask follow-up questions") -(SN6) According to Amadora (2020), "Truth be told, our country is an internet-challenged country. A problem that has caused delays in implementing remote learning in general. Although internet plans exist, they are not, however, created equal. Hence, in online classes, there is never a day when a student hasn't voiced complaints such as "Can someone tell the professor I/he/she got disconnected?" "Oops! Where did he go? (Referring to the professor who doesn't realize he got cut off), "I have unstable Wi-Fi," "Do you guys see/hear me?" "Face to face kasi may physical interactions dama mo or nakikita mo mismo yung mga actions ng professor kung paano nila tinuturo yung mga lessons and procedures". - (SN5) ("During face-to-face, there are physical interactions that you can really appreciate or see the actions of your professors in how they teach the lessons and perform procedures.") - (SN5) "Due to the lack of interaction during online class, we tend to get distracted easily on our smartphones, our pets and deliveries rather than the ongoing class lessons" Amadora (2020). Communication problems are not just affected technically by internet connections but also by how the instructions are given. The participants gave comparisons as, during face-to-face classes, communication is considered good, unlike during online learning, where several factors such as the internet, technicalities, and audio clarity might hinder communication. Participants agree that communication problems might hinder learning as they experience these types of barriers to learning. This proved that communication problems were one challenge that online learners face as they engage in online learning platforms.

E. Insufficient learning method

Learning methods are an important tool in learning. Learning methods provide a critical and logical pattern for how professors facilitate learners learning. Learning methods make the learning process organized and objective for the goals of learning. Insufficient learning methods are one of the perceived barriers to learning participants encounter. Since nursing is a skill-based profession, skill-based training is a must, but limitations from the threat of pandemics hinder everyone's desire to do the appropriate learning. ("We have to do the real thing, so for us to not be able to do our demonstrations at the RLE lab. ") -(SN3) "Hindi ko natatanggap yung gusto kong kind of learning wala yung optimal

learning na gusto kong mangyari lalo na nasa medical field tayo parang hindi siya applicable sa atin". -(SN6) According to Regalado M. (2020). The reality is that some courses are harder to transfer online, like in fundamentals of nursing, where return demonstrations are a needed procedure that nurses should perform as part of their nursing responsibilities. The COVID- 19 pandemics will most likely continue to present the tests online. This proves that online learning has challenges, especially for courses like BS Nursing that need skill-based training and procedural demonstrations and return demonstrations. ("I didn't get the learning that I wanted. The optimal learning, I want to happen, especially in the medical field, is somehow not applicable to us.") - (SN6) It was stated in the article of Santos (2020) that online learning offers injustice or inequities to students who are engaged in online learning. The Department of Education (DepEd) and the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), which oversees colleges and universities, put together distance learning options that include online platforms. This, however, predisposes the students who need skills-based training to insufficient learning methods. Skill-based courses like nursing require skill-based training to become a skilled professional. However, this pandemic hinders participants from achieving that. Online learning poses a tremendous challenge to future skill-based professionals as they experience that online learning does not give them the optimal learning that they must achieve throughout the process of learning in their chosen profession. This proves that insufficient learning methods are considered a perceived barrier to learning by participants as they engage in online learning.

F. No learning benefits

"No learning benefits" is a statement used by most learners, specifically the participants, because, based on their own experience, they don't see anything practical for them and their academic performance. Most of the learners in the medical field have been struggling with how they will be able to learn with just the technology in front of them effectively. They see online learning as something that they can't fully grasp and be able to quickly adapt to due to the lack of the usual ways of learning and other barriers that can hinder them from acquiring the expected knowledge. From the perspective of some participants, they believe that online learning has no benefits for their academic performance. They do not see it as beneficial face-to-face because they can't get enough resources. They are not learning their topics holistically and perceive this new curriculum as unrealistic compared to what they expected of learning effectively by communicating and interacting while using their holistic approach to learning. According to Baticulon, Sy, Alberto et al. (2021), each medical school developed its own rules for learning activities, altered assessment measures, and established promotion rules after being forced to switch to an online curriculum. As a result, the learning experiences varied between medical schools across the country. The student network of the Association of Philippine Medical Colleges called for the suspension of online learning and the end of the current semester in an open letter posted on social media, citing difficulties that students had faced, including poor internet connection, limited access to gadgets, and a lack of study space at home. In their study, they also added that in Philippine medical education, traditional teaching methods (i.e., teacher-led, classroom-based learning activities) remained the norm. From what they have gathered from different learners from different schools prior to the pandemic, they said they only set aside 8 hours per week for self-directed learning. As a result, the students had difficulty adjusting to the abrupt change in curriculum delivery, which necessitated a simultaneous adjustment in learning styles. "Hindi ko alam kung may benefit kasi nasa internet na lang yung sources ng mga information" -(SN5) (I can't really tell if there is a benefit because sources of information are readily available on the internet.") -(SN5) "In terms sa academic wala akong maisip na benefit sa akin" -(SN6) ("In terms of academic, I couldn't think of anything that would benefit me") -(SN6) Baticulon, Sy, Alberto et al. (2021) also mentioned in their study that medical students in the Philippines questioned if their colleges were ready to adapt to online learning. They claimed a lack of rules, unfair procedures, erratic class scheduling, poor quality teaching materials, inefficient teaching tactics, and burdensome class requirements as reasons for their dismissal. Academic medical centers in Singapore, by contrast, have precisely defined permitted undergraduate teaching activities and assessments based on their pandemic alert level. Medical schools in New York devised a strategic plan that allowed students to meet their graduation requirements on schedule and eased the transition to residency. ("We only do our procedures with a dummy, right? So that is already somewhat unrealistic; what more if we have to improvise? So that's the disadvantage; we are not holistically learning about nursing. ") -(SN3) This proves that with proper planning and implementation, the learners will be able to attain the expected benefits that they usually get before a pandemic, such as hands-on activities, a holistic approach to patients, and the ability to correct mistakes quickly as they can interact. Based on the situation of the participants, if proper implications and handling will arise for online learning, they can achieve the expected outcomes that a learner should get. When the goal of planning was

easily achieved, However, if this fails, results may be expected as the inability to appreciate the true importance and benefits of online learning, such as easy accessibility to learning, and possibly affect their academic performance due to their being unmotivated based on their actions and way of thinking.

G. Relying too much on technology

As a result of the threat of a pandemic, technology is considered a big help during the shift from traditional learning to online learning. However, some learners see this as a challenge and opt to engage in online learning. Relying too much on technology is a disadvantage, as not every learner is inclined to use technological devices for online learning. The use of computers and other online platforms to accomplish a task is considered a challenge for the participants as they encounter issues about how to use such technological tools for learning. The inability of the learners to use technology as a tool in learning hinders them from accomplishing specific tasks, which predisposes them to rely too much on technology as a challenge. "Naging disadvantage din yung masyado tayong nakarely sa technologies" -(SN1) ("Relying too much on technology makes an advantage for us") -(SN1) It was concluded in the study by Kulesza et al. (2011). It is clear that technology must be correctly managed and moderated to lessen its negative characteristics and strengthen the positive ones. Some risks of using technology in education are less interest in what is being taught, more distractions, less participation in the classroom, and making learning and teaching more difficult. ("As a student, it's so easy for us to scroll through our lectures, sometimes even neglected, so that's the downside.") -(SN3) ("While your professor is discussing, you're actively searching the web for further information.") -(SN3) Technology must be used at a suitable time for solving an actual problem and be accomplished by teachers. This explains some universal best practices when it comes to technology in the classroom. Among these are keeping lectures thought-provoking and energetic to fight the interruptions of technology, setting restrictions on technology use, using technology to connect rather than teach, using technology only when it functions better than previous methods, and creating the choice to change technology when it inhibits learning, Kulesza et al. (2011). This simply proves that technology does not only offer innovations and accessibility, but it also has its downside. For some who are inclined to use technology such as gadgets and online platforms for online learning, it might be considered an advantage, but for those who are not, it is regarded as a challenge. The participants currently experience this particular challenge of online learning as they engage in online learning.

H. Limited virtual discussion

Online learning is a challenge faced by every medical student. Understanding the limited virtual discussion is very important for participants because it can contribute to how much participants are learning in this online setup. This signifies that participant lack skills-based training. According to e-Learning (n.d.), even if a virtual professor can establish a proper virtual environment where the class can work, the absence of a physical presence at a school might be a limitation for an online program. For both instructors and students, things like being left out of meetings and other events that need on-site interaction might be a limiting factor in an online program. As a result, the limited virtual discussion is a challenge posed by online teaching and learning methodology. This will not compensate for the benefits that physical presence gives the learners. "Very limited lang yung time natin ngayong virtual" -(SN6) ("Our time on this virtual learning setup is very limited") -(SN6) Thus, the limited virtual discussion is considered by the participants as one of the challenges that hinders their learning. Time is one of the contributing factors why limited virtual challenges are one of the experiences of the participants as they engage in online learning.

THEME 4 - Environmental Barriers to Learning

Environmental barriers are the participants' physical barriers that directly affect the learning process. Participants view environmental barriers as one of the opposing sides of online learning. Moreover, the participants consider environmental barriers and problems they encounter as they engage in online learning. Environmental barriers include internet connection issues, and uncondusive learning environment, a lack of technical skills, and limited learning resources.

SUBTHEMES:

A. Internet connection issue

The internet allows students to interact with their teachers or classmates via Google Classroom, Zoom, Messenger Apps, Chat Forums, etc. The connection is convenient for the student; it allows them to search for information, scan, and browse the internet, which helps the student complete their homework. Due to the pandemic, some students have internet

connection problems, which can affect their studies. In many circumstances, you can resolve internet connection problems on your own. Only in extreme circumstances should you call your internet service provider. Nowadays, when students use various digital devices such as desktops, laptops, smartphones, tablets, and other devices, it is critical to understand how to fix internet connectivity difficulties. “Normally di naman talaga lahat na mabilis ang internet connection lalo dito sa amin sa province di ganun kabilis talaga yung internet connection so talagang nahihirapan ako na magpasa ng mga assignments ganun or ng mga works” -(SN1) (“Not everyone has a fast internet connection, especially those of us who are in our provinces. The internet connection is so slow and it affects how we submit our assignments and other work.”) -(SN1) According to Chua and Sibbaluca (n.d), in general, students enjoy the e-learning platforms used by their professors. However, some could not get connected due to slow connections or because they had no capacity to produce the resources. For some students, this is their first time utilizing these platforms, and they have difficulty accessing them. They have limited time to learn how to use them, thus delaying the submission of their assignments online. “Di lahat ng mga student’s kaya yung malakas na internet. So yun yung pinaka siguro mahirap ngayong online class. May mga students na di nakakapasok dahil mahina ang internet connection.” -(SN2) (“Not all students have a fast internet connection. Therefore, that is the most difficult scenario during online classes. There are students that can’t attend classes because of a slow internet connection.”) -(SN2). According to Jones (2019), access to the internet connection and learning devices continues to be a privilege up to this day, placing those with poor internet access at a disadvantage when it comes to online classes. (“We can’t possibly make our internet connection stronger because, of course, there are a lot of external factors that play into it, such as your service provider. There is also the weather. There are a lot of things that play a factor in how good your internet connection is, and I think the quality of online learning also depends on the quality of your internet connection.”) -(SN3) “Wala akong wifi data lang ang ginagamit ko at minsan mahina yung data kaya mahirap” -(SN5) (“I don’t have wifi. I only used data and sometimes my data connection is poor.”) -(SN5) “Sa community kasi nag kakaroon ng unexpected na outlitch ng kuryente fourth yung sa internet” -(SN6) (“In the community, there is unexpected leaching electricity in connection to the internet.”) -(SN6) According to Baticulon R. and SY J. 2020, one out of five students did not have a computer, and an identical proportion had to rely on prepaid mobile data for connectivity. Roughly one in twenty uses only a smartphone. Power interruptions, weak infrastructure, and high internet costs restricted the students’ access to online content. Therefore, in many circumstances, internet connection issues affect the quality of education each student gets. This proves that most of the students may lose internet connections during online learning, resulting in the learner’s inability to complete homework, and some of the learners suffer from a system glitch, the crashing of the application, sudden removal from an ongoing class, the incompatibility of the application on specific devices, and so on. Although a lousy internet connection might also create audio issues, the sort of microphone utilized may also be a factor. Problems with undesired echo and background noises, whether from the lecturer or the student reciting, usually distract learners.

B. Unconducive learning environment

A conducive learning environment is a site free of physical and emotional intimidation, allowing for the open exchange of ideas. An environment that will enable learners to learn more efficiently is considered essential as a conducive learning environment directly affects learning. A conducive environment must be present for learners to achieve the learning they need and need support. Participants see a non-conducive learning environment as an environmental barrier to learning as they engage in online learning. “Wala namang masyadong na develop kasi nasa dorm lang naman ako”. -(SN5) (“There was a little bit of no development at all because I’m just in my dorm.”) -(SN5) Baticulon, R. et al. (2020) stated that many obstacles to online learning were pre-existing, with differences between subgroups being heightened by the pandemic, often favoring those with greater access to resources. This leads to an unequal learning environment, albeit unintended, and the most significant challenge for professors is to ensure that this inequity is not perpetuated. “One thing pa is yung environment, mas okay yung environment sa school kesa dito sa bahay lalo na dito sa amin sobrang gulo yun yung mga ayaw ko” -(SN6) (“Another thing is the environment; I prefer the school environment rather than staying at a messy and crowded place like ours; things I didn’t like.”) -(SN6) According to Baticulon et al. (2020), the learning environment may be virtual, with physical space remaining vital. Having a quiet study area with the same comfort provided by a classroom or library was a privilege not available to all. This simply proves that an unconducive learning environment is one of the many possible challenges participants encounter as they engage in online learning. It is not a new problem in learning but a pre-existing one that will also arise as the shift from traditional learning to online learning continues.

C. Lack of technical skills

During this period of pandemic, learners who study online have access to learning resources and activities at their leisure, allowing them to study whenever and wherever they choose. When things go wrong, however, providing technical help can be challenging, and despite the existence of mobile devices, not all students own them. And embracing technical skills is a must for every medical student to have. However, upon interviewing, some participants still lack technical skills. Unfamiliarity can add up to anxiety, as the participants were clueless. According to Aborajoo et al. 2020, in Jordan, distance learning in clinical medical education is being used to combat the COVID-19 epidemic; the present state of affairs, difficulties, and prospects Because knowing technological, financial, institutional, educator, and student hurdles is critical for the effective adoption of distance learning in medical education, comprehending technical, economic, institutional, educator, and student hurdles are crucial. According to Claudiu C et al. (2020), access to such platforms was occasionally limited, and there were also connectivity issues, mainly when the number of pupils connected was large. Furthermore, 14.8 percent of respondents mentioned that students' lack of adequate technology for participating in online learning has overlapped with these issues (poor internet connection, lack of laptops/computers, mobile connection that partially provides access to resources provided by teachers and platforms). "Paggamit ng google meet or mga zoom di kasi ako familiar talaga sa ganto" -(SN1) ("When using Google Meet and Zoom, I encounter difficulties because I am not familiar with it.") -(SN1) "Problem ko rin yung computer yung mga technology nga na di nga kasi ako familiar di ako techy na person so nahirapan din ako don." (SN1) Online classes will be more difficult for those with minimal computer skills. In addition to understanding the course subject and the instructor's expectations, these individuals must master computer skills simultaneously. This is not necessarily a disadvantage because they will profit immensely. Nevertheless, more time will be required to deal with the learning curve of acquiring the requisite computer skills. Of course, attending a face-to-face course will almost certainly necessitate computer skills, so it is prudent to accept them anyway. Online education is likely to be a little more difficult at first. ("Another problem is the computer, since I don't know/I am not familiar with the use of technology; I am not a techy person. That is why it is quite difficult for me. ") -(SN1) ("So, for me personally, I would do much better face-to-face. Also, I am not techy, so that's another problem. ") (SN3) Thus, lack of technical skills and necessary unmet skills were barriers to learning and are a challenge for students in this online course set-up. Participants view a lack of technical skills as an environmental barrier that hinders learning.

D. Limited learning resources

Given the success of online learning in clinical education, the main impediment to its implementation is a lack of resources in medical schools and the needed supplies for the students in the safety of their homes. Due to the inability of learners to go out of their houses because of the pandemic, they couldn't provide their own supply of school needs to comply with their requirements. According to Baticulon, R.E., Sy, J.J., Alberto, N.R.I., et al. (2021), medical students in the Philippines faced social and cultural obstacles and inadequate access to technological resources during the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, the economic ramifications of the pandemic widened inequalities in medical education, favoring those with better access to resources. ("The videos that the professors send us are either from the US or somewhere overseas; it's not Philippine based and it's hard because we don't have much material when we do our demos"). -(SN3) "It is really hard at first, kasi yung resources is limited". -(SN5) ("It's really hard at first, because resources are limited") -(SN5) With that said, resources play a major role in the learning process as they can supply the learners with a visual representation of what they are currently learning. Hence, it will make it easier for the learners to visualize the actual thing even if they are virtually interacting with the educator

THEME 5 - ADAPTATION APPROACHES TO ONLINE LEARNING

Adaptation approaches to online learning are participants' coping strategies for adapting to the challenges of online learning. Theme 5 shows the common strategy of the participants on how they manage challenges encountered as they engage in online learning. Time management, pacing options, leisure to cope, technical skills to use gadgets for online learning, multitasking, and staying up-to-date are all adaptation approaches to online learning.

SUBTHEMES:

A. Time management

Time management refers to students' ability to use their time effectively or productively. It is convenient because it allows them to prioritize their work and guarantees that they have adequate time to finish their activities. It will enable the learners to complete their tasks in less time because their attention is focused and away from distractions. The pandemic

shined a light on the considerable challenge that acquiring time-management skills presents. Time management is an important skill, one would say essential to academic success in our classes. During online learning, the students practice time management at home without direct supervision from teachers. Therefore, learners depend on their own discipline to control their home learning time. "Pagonline tayo yung time management natin kung baga magkaroon tayo ng time na makasama yung family natin pero at the same time nakakapag study pa rin tayo" -(SN1) ("In online [learning], we can manage our time so that we can have time to be with our family but at the same time we can still study." -(SN1) According to Baticulon R. (2020), educators must understand learners' needs, motivations, and past experiences to maintain engagement in an online curriculum. To achieve academic success, students need to be guided in developing self-regulated learning strategies, which include time management. "Nagpapriority ako ng mga gagawin for example sa mga major subjects. Syempre mas andami nilang gagawin, uunahin ko muna yung mga major o kaya ano yung binigay na task ngayon yun na yung gagawin ko para di na siya sabay sabay" -(SN1) ("I prioritize things to do, for example, in major subjects. Of course, there are a lot of tasks to do. I will prioritize first the majors or whatever task is given now. That's what I will do so that it won't be piled up. ") (SN1) According to Francisco C. and Barcelona M. (2020), time management could be properly handled due to more tasks being accomplished. It maximizes time so the learner can still attend to other important matters, whether personal or professional in nature. It's easy to take online learning seriously. With regular classroom learning, learners have a specific place they need to be at a particular time. But, learning online requires them to set aside some time on their own to study and go through the lessons. This requires discipline and a fundamental understanding of how to use their time throughout the day wisely. "Kadalasan kasi meron ako mga reminders so talagang hinahati hati ko mga gagawin ko" -(SN2) ("Usually, I have reminders so I divided what I do/ usually i have a reminder so i can divide my time to do what i have to") -(SN2) ("Managing my time and making sure that I'm ahead of the deadlines because you don't know when the internet is going to have issues so, me personally, I like to do all of my assessments as soon as they're given") -(SN3) "Ngayong online classes talagang maraming binibigay na activities kahit anong oras nagbibigay sila ng activities kaya kailangan talaga ng time management" (SN4) ("Now in online classes, they really give us a lot of activities at any time, regardless of the time. They give us activities, so time management is really needed.") (SN4) "Yung time management ko parang pomodoro technique kaso ang pomodoro technique ko is mas longer yung rest kesa sa study kaya siguro hindi naging effective sakn yung time management ko" -(SN6) ("My time management is like a pomodoro technique, but in my case, my pomodoro technique has a longer rest than the study, so maybe my time management hasn't been effective for me") -(SN6) According to Baticulon (2020), to achieve academic success, students need to be guided in developing self-regulated learning strategies, which include time management, metacognition, critical thinking, and effort regulation. Time management benefits learners, as participants consider it the best adaptation to online learning. With time management, participants would be able to logically and systematically plan and control their time for learning. The transition from a face-to-face class to online learning increases the risk of failure to complete certain tasks. However, participants were able to manage the challenges of online learning by using time management as a coping mechanism or adaptive behavior.

B. Pacing options

The pacing option is the ability of the learners to control what to achieve first in consideration of the time frame. It differs from time management because the pacing option deals with organizing what to do, while time management deals with tasks with time dimensions. Participants in this study consider pacing options as one of their coping strategies as they engage in online learning. Pacing options make their time flexible, so they can choose when to finish their academic tasks.

"Meron tayong sariling oras na pwede natin gawin yung mga family Gatherings tapos pwede pa rin tayo makapag study" -(SN1) ("we have our own time that we can do family gatherings and then we can still study.")-(SN1) ("it's convenient and you are learning at your own phase") -(SN3) "Yung time kasi hawak mo oras mo kahit may mga schedules na cocontrol padin " -(SN5) In the article by Samoy (2021), it was stated that professors and learners could also interact at their comfort and convenience. It was discussed that learners could control their time and have their own pace for when to do their activities. ("You can manipulate your time, even if there are schedules, you can still control it.") -(SN5) "May mga oras na mahaba ang duration ng pasahan ganun di kagaya ng face to face na biglaan" -(SN2) ("There are times when the duration of submission of activity is much longer compared to face-to-face, which is submitted in a much shorter time") -(SN2) According to Francisco C. & Barcelona M. (2020), during online classes or the use of specific online platforms, the learner could still be present for other important matters, whether personal or professional in nature. It's easy to take online learning seriously. With regular classroom learning, learners have a specific place they need to be at a specific

time. But, learning online requires them to set aside some time on their own to study and go through the lessons. The pacing option is considered a good adaptation approach during online learning. Participants use this to control what to do first, considering the time and pace to accomplish a certain task. Pacing holds promise for some learners who have difficulty organizing their tasks by what to do first. This makes the participants practice systematic and logical planning to accomplish their responsibilities as learners.

C. Leisure to cope

Leisure activities pose freedom from work, school, and other types of responsibilities. At some point in time, leisure activities like bonding with families and doing things the learners enjoy are helpful to divert the learner's attention from the stress of online classes. The shift from traditional learning to online learning because of the pandemic threat poses new challenges. As participants engage in online learning, they encounter these challenges, and as a result, coping strategies are created. One of the many adaptations of the participants was leisure time to cope with the challenges posed by online learning. "So kasi diba pag nasa online learning tayo, nagkakaroon tayo, especially kami na sa province, nagkakaroon kami ng time with our family" -(SN1) ("So, when we are in online learning, we have time, especially those in the province, we have time with our family." -(SN1) "Kasama ko naman din yung family ko dito so kapag naiistress ako pupuntahan ko muna sila ganun lalo na kasi may baby kami ditto so ayun." (SN1) ("I'm also with my family here, so when I'm stressed, I'll go to them first, especially because we have a baby here.") -(S According to Esiahdonkoh (2014), learners continued to employ recreational skill approaches to cope with stressful events rather than physical or socio-psychological approaches. This sort of learner usually takes things slowly and methodically and can easily grip herself when challenges emerge. ("If you're talking about leisure, the coping mechanism would be sleep, definitely sleep") -(SN3) "Manood ng anime movies tapos pag na feel ko na eenergize na ako, naiisip ko na time na para mag-aral ayun yung nakaka motivate sa akin" -(SN6) ("Watching anime movies and when I feel energized, I think it's time to study. That's what motivates me") -(SN6) According to Shamsuddin et al. (2013), although the use of remote learning confronts immediate educational challenges, learners handle these challenges by diverting their focus to recreational events. Students that are stressed out use this coping mechanism consistently. This simply proves that the participants encounter challenges as they engage in online learning. Participants also formulate adaptive strategies to cope with such challenges. Online learning offers many challenges, hindering a learner's ability to focus on learning. Leisure can help to alleviate the frustrations of online learning challenges. In this study, leisure activities are considered by the participants as a form of adaptive approach as they engage in online learning. The participants enjoy leisure activities such as bonding with their families and watching movies, and they recognize that such activities are beneficial.

D. Technical skills to use gadgets for online learning

The advancement of technology is radically altering societal standards. Both educated and unskilled people utilize technology to enjoy and gain from it. Different social media platforms, such as Facebook, WhatsApp, and Twitter, have been seen to play an essential part in education. These applications drew in a large number of pupils and allowed them to interact with people from all around the world. These programs introduce pupils to a range of new educational terms, one of which is e-learning. Thus, this signifies that participants' heavy workloads were uplifted due to the advanced development of technologies. E-learners desire to use new technologies to learn and interact with individuals who are interested in their subject. (Anshari, Alas, & Guan, 2016). E-learning is being used to promote education in many places throughout the world. On the other hand, everyone wishes to improve their education at any cost and in every way possible. According to Bevan M. (2020), today's students use educational films to learn everything from basic skills, such as changing a tire, to the next dance fad. Surprisingly, millennials account for 92 percent of all digital video viewers. Now that there are good instructional video platforms for online learning, abstract ideas that used to be hard to teach and understand are now easier to teach and understand. "Yun sa pageedit ng mga videos natuto rin ako kung paano sila ipagcombine. Natututo din ata akong maggawa ng powerpoint" -(SN1) ("I learned how to edit videos and how to combine them. I also learned how to make a powerpoint") -(SN1) "Video na lang pinapasa namin so para sa amin advantage yun kasi nagagawa namin at naeedit namin" -(SN2)("we submit the video [RetDem], so for us that's an advantage because we can do it and we can edit it") -(SN2) ("we get to be familiar with technology which would help us in future research.") -(SN3) "Ginagamit natin ngayong mga technologies hindi na kailangan ng mga paper ngayong screenshot nalang save mo lang sa phone mo mas okay din kasi nga marunong naman tayo sa mga computers". -(SN4) ("Now we use technology, we no longer use paper anymore, just take a screenshot and save it on your phone, it's much better because we

know how to use computers”). - (SN4) Therefore, the use of gadgets for online learning to gain skills is evident through the studies which show students using them as a tool for learning everything, including educational platforms. The use of technical skills for online learning is considered an effective adaptation approach by the participants as they engage and encounter the challenges of online learning.

E. Multitasking

In this time of the pandemic, where online learning continues to be included in our everyday lives as learners, one of the things that an individual does to cope with the struggles of a pile of schoolwork and loads of notes to study is to multitask. Multitasking does wonders for learners to make it easy for them to finish their job on time, and they consider it a skill that they have recently adapted with the help of online learning. Multitasking has become a mantra in our culture, one that has been repeated and accepted indiscriminately so many times that it has become commonplace—not only in casual conversation but also among generally astute academics. People in general, and our learners in particular, can and do work productively and learn efficiently while doing multiple things at once, according to this generally held assumption. According to Lepp (2019), students' multitasking behavior in online courses is substantially higher than in face-to-face classes, according to the findings of the study. Additionally, students who prefer to multitask do indeed multitask more than students who do not prefer to multitask in online courses. However, in face-to-face courses, students who prefer to multitask do not multitask more frequently than students who do not prefer to multitask. "This is likely because, in face-to-face courses, a physically present teacher and the presence of conscientious students help to enforce classroom policies and behavioral norms against multitasking," Dr. Lepp said. "Kagaya nga po yung may ipapasang retdem may exam may quiz ganun tapos biglang may ipapapasa ulit" -(SN2) ("Like when I need to submit a retdem [video], there's also an exam, a quiz, and suddenly there's another activity that needs to be submitted again.") (SN2) ("It's developing my character and my patience and enhancing my computer skills, my multitasking") -(SN3) ("You are doing a lot of things; you're learning a lot of things.") -(SN3) "Siguro mas na improve ko yung pagiging multitasking ko kasi minsan pinagsasabay ko na yung mga gawain sa mga subjects ko" -(SN6) ("Maybe I improved a lot with my multitasking [skills] because sometimes I can do some of the activities at once in different subjects.") -(SN6) Even if multitasking during online learning is very efficient in lessening the workload all at the same time, it is still advisable to minimize this kind of practice for the learner to know still the importance of focusing and finishing work one at a time, as what Dr. Lepp advised in his study for those students who are excessively multitasking with other tasks that are not relevant.

F. Always updated

With limited access to the internet and resources, staying updated on announcements is already crucial for participants. Participants were just forced to correct for the sake of learning online. According to Kadir, A. et al. (n.d.), students who use e-learning admit that the notion really benefits them in their studies. Some findings are that e-learning impacts students' self-efficacy, particularly in updating their knowledge and abilities to grasp new ideas presented at school. "Awareness na lang din kung ano yung bago sa mga tinuturo" -(SN1) ("Just being aware of what is new in what is being taught") -(SN1) ("You have to be vigilant; you have to stay alert; you don't know when a professor will drop a quiz; you don't know when an assignment will be assigned to you.") -(SN3) Thus, a sudden change in the new learning set-up resulted in the student's new way of adapting to the online set-up being updated or upgraded with new learning. Participants' views being constantly updated is one of the adaptive approaches to the challenges of online learning. The participants also view this particular adaptive approach as an effective experience in dealing with tasks and responsibilities as they engage with online learning.

V. SUMMARY

The pandemic poses many challenges and modifications to the educational system in the Philippines, especially in tertiary education. Skill-based allied health courses such as BS nursing require skill-based training. However, because of the pandemic threat, limitations were placed on how learning would continue, and, from this, a phenomenon was established. This study explores the experiences of nursing students from Mary Chiles College Manila. Participants in online learning have gone through emotional and psychological changes, such as a lack of motivation, which made it hard for them to deal with online learning. Moreover, adjusting to online learning forced learners to deal with such changes: the lack of confidence it caused since they were afraid to answer direct questions in online discussions and the anxiety they felt because they didn't have a support system. This experience was due to a lack of support from family, friends, and others as they also compared themselves, such as in the availability of resources as they engaged in online learning.

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (166-189), Month: September - December 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Online learning doesn't cause adverse effects. As participants engaged in online learning, the following compliments were received: online learning is convenient; online learning is the best substitute for face-to-face; learning resources are available; independent learning is possible; and professors' efforts are recognized. These pertain to perceived complements resulting from online teaching and learning methodology. Participants visualize perceived compliments as positive feedback on online learning. As participants engaged in online learning, challenges such as the physical presence of teaching online learning were a challenging application to professional communication problems; insufficient learning methods; no learning benefits; relying too much on technology; and limited virtual discussions arose.

Environmental barriers are the physical limitations that directly affect the participants' engagement in the learning process. As participants engage in online learning, barriers arise, such as Internet connection issues, an un conducive learning environment, a lack of technical skills, and limited learning resources. This pertains to the environmental barriers to learning. These specific environmental barriers were seen as common among participants. In order to cope with such challenges and barriers, strategies were developed that were common among participants. As participants engage in online learning, adaptations to online learning developed by participants to cope with this include time management, pacing options, leisure to cope with, technical skills to use gadgets for online learning, multitasking, and always staying updated. This pertains to adaptation approaches for online learning. These adaptation approaches are the strategies participants used to counteract the negatives of online learning.

VI. CONCLUSION

From the viewpoint of the participants, this study revealed the essence of adaptation to online learning in a broad scope across all nursing schools. The participants who took part in online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic are subjected to emotional and psychological advantages and disadvantages that are associated with their thoughts, feelings, and behavioral responses to the experience of online learning. The study also showed that although online learning is a viable substitute for traditional education, giving a positive outcome in academic performance, most participants still emphasized their concerns regarding their experiences in online learning. Every statement was identified as the same situation as the other. The researchers also concluded that themes and subthemes were interrelated with each other, meaning that when a problem arose, the participant perceived that it was present, and it also had an effect on their other concerns, which can be seen as a connection. Lastly, the researchers concluded that emotional and psychological experiences, perceived complements, perceived challenges, environmental learning barriers, and adaptation approaches to online learning provided answers to the study grand tour question: how do you describe your online learning experiences?

REFERENCES

Book

- [1] Morrow, R., Rodriguez, A. and King, N. (2015). Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenological method. *The Psychologist*, 28(8), 643-644.
- [2] Polit, D & Beck, C. (2018). *Essentials of Nursing Research*. 9th ed. Pg275-277. LIPPINCOTT WILLIAMS & WILKINS, a WOLTERS. Philadelphia US.
- [3] Rovai, 2002. A constructivism approach to online college learning. *Internet and higher education*, 7, 79-93.
- [4] Online Websites and Journals
- [5] Anderson, T. D. et.al., D. R. (2002). *Critical Inquiry in a Text-Based Environment: Computer Conferencing in Higher Education*. Retrieve on 01/05/2020, Retrieve from Anderson, T. D. et.al., D. R. (2002). *Critical Inquiry in a Text-Based Environment: Computer Conferencing in Higher Education*.
- [6] Abaté, C. J. (2008). *You Say Multitasking Like It's a Good Thing*. Retrieved from National Education Association: <http://www.clausentech.com/lchs/dclausen/algebra2/NEA%20Multitasking%20Article%20-%20Fall%202008.pdf>
- [7] Anderson, T. D. et.al., D. R. (2002). *Critical Inquiry in a Text-Based Environment: Computer Conferencing in Higher Education*. Retrieve on 01/05/2020, Retrieve from Anderson, T. D. et.al., D. R. (2002). *Critical Inquiry in a Text-Based Environment: Computer Conferencing in Higher Education*.

- [8] Akbari, O., & Sahibzada, J. (2020). Students' Self-Confidence and Its Impacts on Their Learning Process.
- [9] Al-Balas, M. (2020). Distance learning in clinical medical education amid COVID-19 pandemic in Jordan: current situation, challenges, and perspectives. Retrieved from <https://bmcmededuc.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12909-020-02257-4>
- [10] Al-Amin, M., Zubayer, A. A., Deb, B., & Hasan, M. (2021, January 7). Status of tertiary level online class in Bangladesh: students' response on preparedness, participation and classroom activities. Retrieved from Science Direct: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405844021000487>
- [11] Amadora, M. (2020). Manila Bulletin: Common Problems that Occur During Online Classes. Retrieve on 05/27/21. Retrieve from <https://mb.com.ph/2020/09/18/common-problems-that-occur-during-online-classes/>
- [12] Azzahra (2020) The Philippine Higher Education Sector in the Time of COVID-19. Retrieved from Frontiers | The Philippine Higher Education Sector in the Time of COVID-19 | Education (frontiersin.org)
- [13] Baticulon R. and SY J. (2020). Barriers to Online Learning in the Time of COVID-19: A National Survey of Medical Students in the Philippines. Retrieved from Barriers to Online Learning in the Time of COVID-19: A National Survey of Medical Students in the Philippines | SpringerLink
- [14] Chua E. and Sibbaluca B. (n.d) THE STATUS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE E- LEARNING CLASSROOM IN SELECTED HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN REGION IV-A AMIDST THE COVID-19 CRISIS. Retrieved from [197-1590731776.pdf \(jcreview.com\)](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341981898_The_COVID-19_Pandemic_through_the_Lens_of_Education_in_the_Philippines_The_New_Normal)
- [15] Claudiu Coman, Maria Cristina Bularca, Luiza Meses, an-Schmitz (n.d) Online Teaching and Learning in Higher Education during the Coronavirus Pandemic: Students' Perspective. Retrieved from [sustainability-12-10367-v2 \(1\).pdf](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341981898_The_COVID-19_Pandemic_through_the_Lens_of_Education_in_the_Philippines_The_New_Normal)
- [16] Cleofas, J. & Rocha, I.C. (2021). Demographic, gadget and internet profiles as determinants of disease and consequence related COVID-19 anxiety among Filipino college students. Retrieve 05/19/21. Retrieved from [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341981898_The_COVID-19_Pandemic_through_the_Lens_of_Education_in_the_Philippines_The_New_N normal](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341981898_The_COVID-19_Pandemic_through_the_Lens_of_Education_in_the_Philippines_The_New_Normal)
- [17] Esiahdonkoh, K. (2014). Stress coping strategies of 2012/2013 final year sandwich students of the department of basic education, university of education, Winneba (UEW), Ghana. *International Journal of Education Learning and Development*, 2(1), 54–67.
- [18] Francisco, C. & Barcelona, M. (2020). Effectiveness of an Online Classroom for Flexible Learning. *International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR)* ISSN: 2643-9670 Vol. 4, Issue 8, and August – 2020, Pages: 100-107. Retrieve on 05/26/21. Retrieve from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED607990.pdf?fbclid=IwAR16VQgUL87rOi3gDEJ2D5c9y0BGUH6zRrxgr2zYU9ZsKXrKDFCtaSIWAHU>
- [19] Jones (2019). The Philippine Higher Education Sector in the Time of COVID-19. Retrieved from Frontiers | The Philippine Higher Education Sector in the Time of COVID-19 | Education (frontiersin.org)
- [20] Jones, A. & Kessler, M. 2020. Teachers' Emotion and Identity Work during a Pandemic. Retrieved from <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2020.583775/full>
- [21] Jones, I. M. (2011). Can You See Me Now? Defining Teaching Presence in the Online Classroom through Building a Learning Community. Retrieved from *Journal of Legal Studies Education*: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1744-1722.2010.01085.x>
- [22] Kadir, A., Yacob, A., Zainudin, O., et. al (2012). Student Awareness Towards E-Learning in Education. Retrieved from (PDF) Student Awareness Towards E-Learning In Education ([researchgate.net](https://www.researchgate.net))
- [23] Kulesza, J. et. al. (2011). More Technology, Less Learning? *Information Systems Education Journal (ISEDJ)*. Retrieve on 05/27/21. Retrieve from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1136848.pdf>

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

 Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (166-189), Month: September - December 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

- [24] Lammers, W. J. (2017, March 24). Why Won't They Ask for Help? Retrieved from Faculty Focus: <https://www.facultyfocus.com/articles/effective-classroom-management/wont-ask-us-help/>
- [25] Lepp, A. (2019, February 14). Multitasking increases in online courses compared to face-to-face. Retrieved from Science Daily: <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2019/02/190214153135.htm>
- [26] Lumen Candela. (n.d.). Effective Online Discussions Retrieved from <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/virtualllearningdesigndelivery/chapter/6-effective-online-discussions/>
- [27] Martineau, M. (2020). Education and COVID-19: challenges and opportunities. Retrieved from Education and COVID-19: challenges and opportunities (ccunesco.ca)
- [28] Moneva, J. C.-o., & Tribunalo, S. M. (2020, May). Students' Level of Self-confidence and PerformanceTasks. Retrieved from Research Gate: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343568936_Students'_Level_of_Self-confidence_and_Performance_Tasks
- [29] Morin, A. (2020). 5 Reasons Students Aren't Engaging in Distance Learning. Retrieved from Child Mind Institute: <https://childmind.org/article/5-reasons-students-arent-engaging-in-distance-learning/amp/>
- [30] Philippines: The New Normal. Strengthening Online Learning Platforms. Page 2. Retrieve on 05/25/2. Retrieve from <https://www.ijpdll.com/download/the-covid-19-pandemic-through-the-lens-of-education-in-the-Philippines-the-new-normal-8311.PD>
- [31] Purdue University Global. (2020). 4 Common Challenges Facing Online Learners and How to Overcome Them. Retrieve on 05/24/2. Retrieve from <https://www.purdueglobal.edu/> Updated June 30, 2020
- [32] Regalado, M. (2020). Challenges amid pandemic Online Learning Experiences Response during the COVID-19 Pandemic of First Year BSN learners. Retrieve on 05/26/21. Retrieve from <https://cavite.lpu.edu.ph>
- [33] Santos, A. (2020). In the Philippines, distance learning reveals the digital divide. Retrieve on 05/26/21. Retrieve from <https://eu.boell.org/en/2020/10/06/philippines-distance-learning-reveals-digital-divide>
- [34] Samoy, H. et al. (2021). From Ladle to Chalk and Pencil: Parents in the New Normal of Philippine Education System. Retrieve on 05/23/21. Retrieve from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341981898_The_COVID-19_Pandemic_through_the_Lens_of_Education_in_the_Philippines_The_New_Normal
- [35] Shamsuddin, K., Fadzil, F., Ismail, W. S. W., Shah, S. A., Omar, K., Muhammad, N. A., Jaffar, A., Ismail, A., Mahadevan, R. (2013). Correlates of depression, anxiety and stress among Malaysian university students. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 6 (4), 318–323. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2013.01.014>
- [36] Segaren, S. (2020). 5 major benefits of online learning. Retrieved from <https://www.studyinternational.com/news/benefits-online-learning/>
- [37] Tria, Z. (2020). The COVID-19 Pandemic through the Lens of Education in the Philippines: The New Normal. Strengthening Online Learning Platforms. Page 2. Retrieve on 05/25/2. Retrieve from <https://www.ijpdll.com/download/the-covid-19-pandemic-through-the-lens-of-education-in-the-philippines-the-new-normal-8311.pdf>
- [38] Thompson, C. & Sheckley, B.G. (1997). Differences in classroom teaching preferences between traditional and adult BSN students. *Journal of Nursing Education*. 36.163- 169.
- [39] Yuan Qing Jin. (2021). A Study on Traditional Teaching Method Transferring to E-Learning Under the Covid-19 Pandemic: From Chinese Students' Perspectives retrieved from *Frontiers | A Study on Traditional Teaching Method Transferring to E-Learning Under the Covid-19 Pandemic: From Chinese Students' Perspectives | Psychology (frontiersin.org)*